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Halal destination attributes and its relationship with destination image based on local wisdom and revisit intention

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Abstract

This article will add in comprehending the attributes of halal destination and its relationship with destination image based on local wisdom and revisit intention. The design of this study is a literature review, which conducts a search and literature research by reading and studying a variety of books, journals, and other published manuscripts linked to research subjects. The terms "Islamic Destination," "Indonesian Halal Destination," "Halal Destination Attributes," "Halal Destination Tourist," "Destination Image," "Local Wisdom" and "Revisit Intention" are utilised. The chosen articles are those that satisfy the following requirements for inclusion: original, full-text research publications written in both Indonesian and English, with a maximum journal publishing period of 20 years (2004–2024). Look up research publications that have been published online using open access resources like Scopus and Google Scholar. Based on the literature review that was done it is understand that the link connecting Halal Destination Attributes and Destination Image based on Local Wisdom is synergistic. Destinations that incorporate halal-friendly amenities and services that respect customs and principles of culture can increase their authenticity, involve local communities, and develop a positive image among Muslim tourists.

Keywords: Halal Destinations; Destinations Image; Local Wisdom; Revisit Intention; Halal Destination Attributes; Halal Destination Tourist

1. Introduction

Over the past ten years, there has been a noticeable growth in interest in halal tourism and destinations. The general population continues to lack knowledge about Halal Destination and its features (El-Gohary, 2016; Nofandi et al., 2023; Priyatmoko & Maulana, 2022; Suherlan & Haribowo, 2021). Amir Abdullah et al., 2020; Bazazo et al., 2017; Jafari & Scott, 2014; Jeaheng et al., 2019; Napu & Nurhidayat, 2019; Noviyani & Ratnasari, 2021; Rahmawati et al., 2022; Sriprasert et al., 2014; Utami et al., 2019) are just a few of the studies that indicate that there are still discrepancies among the researchers regarding the Halal Destination attributes. In the tourism industry, it is advised to use "Halal" as a brand name rather than "Islamic," according to Battour (2018). Researchers who used the terms "halal friendly destination" and "halal tourism" (Al-ansi et al., 2020; Auliya et al., 2020; Sulaiman et al., 2022) have validated this. However, there are still differences that exist between the concept of the qualities of a Halal destination and the paradigm of a general tourism destination (Firdaus et al., 2021; Mawardi, 2022; Priyatmoko & Maulana, 2022).

Al-ansi et al., 2020; Bastaman, 2018; Han et al., 2019; Mawardi, 2022; Muttaqillah et al., 2018; Olya & Al-ansi, 2018; Rahmawati et al., 2021; Sodawan & Hsu, 2022; Sulaiman et al., 2022) did, however, differ somewhat from previous research on studies on halal hospitality and its attributes in local contexts.

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In non-Muslim nations, such as South Korea (Abukhalifeh et al., 2020; Han et al., 2019; Jeaheng et al., 2019; Marlinda et al., 2023), Thailand (Chanin et al., 2015; Sriprasert et al., 2014), Japan (Saville & Mahbubi, 2021), Slovenia (Šuligoj & Maruško, 2017), and China (Jia & Chaozhi, 2021). All these countries have employed Halal destination attributes. Others (Andriani & Kurriwati, 2022; Auliya et al., 2020; Faza, 2019; Mawardi, 2022; Napu & Nurhidayat, 2019; Nofandi et al., 2023; Parhan et al., 2021; Putra, 2019; Rahayu & Candra, 2023; Rahmawati et al., 2022; Ratnasari et al., 2023; Santoso & Cahyani, 2020; Sobari et al., 2020) concentrated on the origin of Halal destinations in Indonesia.

Additionally, this article will add in comprehending the attributes of halal destination and its relationship with destination image based on local wisdom and revisit intention. Governments, tourism stakeholders, and local communities may benefit greatly from the halal tourism on a global scale in terms of the economy, society, and culture. With this knowledge, there will be opportunities to profit from the growing Muslim tourism industry worldwide and promote inclusive and environmentally friendly tourism strategies.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Definition of Tourism Destination

According to World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) (2007), a destination for tourism is an area that draws visitors due to its natural, man-made, recreational, athletic, and other features. It is characterised as an area that is conducive to tourism and has natural, built-up, and recreational features that draw visitors (Esipova & Gokova, 2020). Different definitions of a tourist destination have been put up by academics based on a variety of factors, including territorial, economic, social, and administrative (Komilova et al., 2021). A tourist destination is also seen of as something that needs to be managed, subject to natural forces, and require marketing strategies and strategic planning (Esipova & Gokova, 2020; Kudriashov & Кудряшов, 2023). The perception of a place is very important in drawing visitors and determining their purpose to behave (Esteves et al., 2022). In summary, the definition of a tourism destination may vary based on individual experiences, preferences, and the information gathered, but the general idea is that a destination is a place where travellers travel, spend some time there, and take advantage of the attractions, facilities, accessibility, and auxiliary services that are provided by a tourism organisation (Jovicic, 2016; Saraniemi & Kylänen, 2011; Tripon & Cosma, 2018; Tsani et al., 2021).

2.2. General Tourism Destination Attributes

Tourist destination attributes, as defined by Jani et al. (2009), are a combination of multifaceted characteristics such as atmosphere, environment, and services that entice visitors to visit and extend their stay. Because travellers can select destinations based on a comparison of available destination qualities, destination management organisations can benefit from understanding travellers' opinions of halal destination attributes (Eom et al., 2020; Park et al., 2014). As previously said, a destination's image is formed in large part by its qualities (Kim, 2014).

According to May-Chiun et al. (2013), there are four aspects for classifying destination attributes: social, cultural/heritage, environmental, and economic. Ragavan et al. (2014) made use of a number of destination attribute-related factors, including Climate, Commodities, Comfort, Culture, People, and Price, in addition to Accommodation and Food Attractions.

Kim (2014) offers a ten-point rating system to gauge both the attachment to a location and the characteristics of an objective in an unforgettable encounter. Moon & Han (2019) used 33 factors pertaining to destination features, including infrastructure, accessibility, destination management, local hospitality, unique activities and events, local culture, infrastructure, and quality of purchase and service.

3. Methods

To produce writing about a certain topic or problem, the design of this study is a literature review, which conducts a search and literature research by reading and studying a variety of books, journals, and other published manuscripts linked to research subjects (Marzali, 2017). The terms "Islamic Destination," "Indonesian Halal Destination," "Halal Destination Attributes," "Halal Destination Tourist," "Destination Image," "Local Wisdom" and "Revisit Intention" are utilised. The chosen articles are those that satisfy the following requirements for inclusion: original, full-text research publications written in both Indonesian and English, with a maximum journal publishing period of 20 years (2004–2024). Look up research publications that have been published online using open access resources like Scopus and Google Scholar.

This systematic literature reviews (SLR) paper uses a qualitative approach to conduct descriptive research. In contrast to experiments, the qualitative descriptive method, according to Sugiyono (2016), is a research approach grounded in post-positivist philosophy that is used to investigate the conditions of natural objects. The researcher uses essential instrument data collection techniques that are carried out in a regulated manner. The qualitative research methods and data analysis employed in this paper highlight the significance of a generalisation. The goal of descriptive research is to provide a more thorough description, explanation, and response to the issue that needs to be investigated by a person, a group, or an event. Humans are the research instruments in qualitative research, and the words or comments they write are based on the real-world circumstances.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Definition of Halal Destination

Over the past twenty years, there has been a growing focus on empirical study on Halal destinations. The analysis includes studies from 2004 to 2024 to show the general trends of the biggest investigations. In the new century, there has been an exponential increase in the quantity of empirical research on Halal Destination in the literature; nevertheless, it is not always obvious how consistent these conclusions are with the earlier attempts. The idea could no longer be valid due to changes in human behaviour throughout time and the complexity of traditional tourism systems. Furthermore, Halal tourism caters to a specific market segment (Eddahar, 2018; Keliat & Sentanu, 2022): Muslim visitors looking for sites and activities that reflect their Islamic views and practices that all will be found in "halal destination". This differs from generic tourist paradigms, which frequently focus on wide appeal and may overlook unique religious or cultural concerns. A "halal destination" is a tourist attraction or travel location that adheres to Islamic laws and regulations.

4.2. Halal Destination Attributes

Islamic attributes of Muslim countries may entice Muslim visitors. Islamic destination features and attributes improve visitor satisfaction and encourage repeat visits (Suid et al., 2017). Travel destinations are defined by their climate, historical heritage, sunshine, scenic beauty, beaches, snow, cultural events, recreational opportunities, benefits of experience, rest and relaxation, self-esteem, prestige, health and fitness, adventure, social interaction, benefits, interests, and the accessibility of marketed imagery. There are two key characteristics of Islamic tourism that can attract Muslim tourists: tangible attributes and intangible attributes. Prayer facilities and halal cuisine are concrete features, but intangible attributes include Islamic entertainment, clothing rules, overall Islamic morality, and Islamic prayer calls (azan) (Battour et al., 2011).

According to Battour et al. (2011), simple access to places of worship (mosques/prayer rooms), easy and halal meals, availability of the Qur'an, and qibla directions. According to Battour et al. (2011), Islamic toilets and entertainment are actual and highly valued attributes. Battour et al. (2011) stated that intangible characteristics are only applicable in Muslim nations because they are unachievable in the context of a westernised non-Muslim culture.

Han et al. (2018) conducts additional study into the features of halal-friendly sites in South Korea, determining the particular impact of attribute elements in influencing destination imagery and behavioural intent. Han et al. (2018) discovered five essential halal-friendly features that can help destination marketers in South Korea create a positive destination image, increase return visits, and boost word-of-mouth behaviour.

Bazazo et al. (2017) discovered that the Islamic attributes of a place, as well as tourist satisfaction, have a substantial impact on destination loyalty. Bazazo et al. (2017) use the following factors to assess the Islamic features of a hotel as part of its destination amenities.

- Availability of religious facilities.
- The Azan can be heard to indicate prayer time.
- Placing a qibla sticker indicating the direction to Makkah in the hotel room.
- Provide copies of the Qur'an in all hotel rooms.
- Access to water supply.
- Availability of Halal food
- Hotels and restaurants offer separate Halal kitchens.
- Hotel amenities include separate swimming pools and gyms for men and women.
- Hotels prohibit pornography.
- Prohibition of alcohol

Further, Han et al. (2018) explores the attributes of halal-friendly destinations in South Korea and identify the specific role of attribute factors in shaping destination image and behavioural intent. Han et al. (2018) found there are five key halal-friendly attributes that can be useful for destination marketers in South Korea to formulate a favourable destination image, obtain repeat visits, and promote word-of-mouth behaviour. Permadi et al. (2021) summarizes the Concept of Halal Tourism Criteria in a destination including Raw Materials, Destinations and Attractions, Human Resources, Accommodation, Facilities at Tourist Attractions, Finance, Marketing and Tourist Targets, Security and Comfort, Accessibility, and Institutions.

The increasing number of Muslims around the world who are looking for travel options that respect their religious practices and beliefs has brought attention to this idea. The following are some essential attributes of a halal destination:

- Halal cuisine: Having access to halal cuisine is one of the most crucial things for Muslim tourists. This refers to food that has been made in accordance with Islamic dietary requirements, meaning it must not contain alcohol or pork, and the meat must have been slaughtered in a way that is permissible (halal slaughter) (Samad et al., 2022; Sodawan & Hsu, 2022).
- Prayer Facilities: Halal locations frequently provide prayer facilities, such as mosques or designated prayer rooms, so Muslims can do their daily prayers in comfort and convenience (Han et al., 2019; Jeaheng et al., 2020; Olya & Al-ansi, 2018).
- Cultural Sensitivity: These places adhere to Islamic traditions and practices, ensuring that cultural standards and sensitivities are maintained. This might include modest clothing standards in public areas or family-friendly lodgings that respect privacy (Beerli-Palacio & Martín-Santana, 2018; Koc, 2020).
- Accommodation Options: Halal-friendly accommodation choices provide separate amenities or services for men and women, for example separate swimming pools, spas, or gyms (Nofandi et al., 2023; Saifudin et al., 2023).
- Islamic Excursions: Some halal places may have Islamic-themed tours or events, such as exploring ancient Islamic sites, taking part in Islamic art training sessions, or hearing talks on Islamic traditions and history (Parhan et al., 2021).
- Ethical behaviours: Halal tourism stresses ethical behaviours such as labour fairness, environmentally friendly practices, and community assistance (Azam et al., 2019; Battour et al., 2021; Solekah et al., 2023).
- Alcohol-Free Environment: Many halal-friendly venues or lodgings do not serve alcohol or have designated alcohol-free areas (Abdrakhmanova & Moghavvemi, 2022; Afifi et al., 2021; COMCEC, 2017).

Based on the review of several studies (Abdrakhmanova & Moghavvemi, 2022; Afifi et al., 2021; Azam et al., 2019; Battour et al., 2011, 2021; Bazazo et al., 2017; Beerli-Palacio & Martín-Santana, 2018; COMCEC, 2017; Han et al., 2018, 2019; Jeaheng et al., 2020; Koc, 2020; Nofandi et al., 2023; Olya & Al-ansi, 2018; Parhan et al., 2021; Permadi et al., 2021; Saifudin et al., 2023; Samad et al., 2022; Sodawan & Hsu, 2022; Solekah et al., 2023), the attributes of halal destinations are understood as the perception of tourism destination attributes consisting of multi-dimensional where it includes the atmosphere, environment and halal services that make tourists to come and stay longer at a destination. The variables of halal destination attributes in this study are formulated and measured in five dimensions of halal destination attributes along with their indicators, namely:

- Provide a halal-friendly social environment.
 - Design and decorate Halal-friendly tourism sites, including paintings, drawings, and architecture.
 - Tourist attractions follow Islamic regulations.
 - Providing a halal-friendly social environment at tourist destinations is convenient.
 - Visitors enjoyed the Halal-friendly social environment at tourist destinations.
 - The social atmosphere of tourist sites is free of illegal goods, such as nightclubs and red-light districts.
 - Muslim travellers enjoy a safe and clean social environment at tourist destinations.
 - Halal-friendly social environments exist in tourist destinations.
- Halal-friendly facilities
 - Ensure easy access to the mosque and prayer room.
 - Halal facilities are available in numerous tourist sites.
 - Tourist sites provide separate halal amenities for men and women, including spas, swimming pools, and gyms.
 - Tourist attractions offer separate prayer rooms for men and women.
- Foods and drinks that are halal.
 - Halal eateries and restaurants at popular tourist destinations prominently show the Halal logo.
 - Halal food and drink served in pristine, secure, and hygienic establishments and tourist destinations.

- Halal certification accredits restaurants serving Halal cuisine in tourist areas.
- Food that is halal is available.
- Halal-compliant services
 - Accessibility of halal information
 - Information on halal services is available at the tourist information centre.
 - Halal services are efficiently provided in several languages (e.g., Arabic, Malay) at tourist attractions.
 - Halal services provided in compliance with Islamic law at tourist destinations.
- Locals and employees who are halal friendly.
 - Local employees at tourist destinations are knowledgeable about Halal goods and services.
 - The local employees are knowledgeable about providing halal goods and services.
 - The people here are well-versed in Halal and Islamic law.

4.3. Halal Destination Attributes and Destination Image based on Local Wisdom

Based on their perceptions, experiences, and expectations, travellers' perceptions of a place are described by the destination image (Anugrah et al., 2022; Bui, 2022; Haliman & Tan, 2023; Kisi, 2019; Mardikaningsih et al., 2023; Mazanec & Strasser, 2007; Mutiara & Anandya, 2023; Pujiastuti et al., 2020; Putri et al., 2014; Siregar et al., 2020).

Building this image requires local knowledge, especially in halal tourism settings that prioritise authenticity and cultural integrity (Muzakir & Suastra, 2024; Noor et al., 2020; Paskasari, 2020; Pribadi et al., 2021; Rochadi, 2018; J. H. E. Sitorus, 2016; Suandari et al., 2023; Sukawati et al., 2021; Sulasmini & Astina, 2018). As a result, local knowledge plays an important part in shaping this picture. Here's how local wisdom influences the destination's image:

- Local knowledge exposes deep cultural customs, beliefs, and practices (Ibrahim et al., 2021; Irfansyah, 2021; Ismail et al., 2014; Purwana, 2018; Wahyuningtyas et al., 2019). Destinations that protect and promote indigenous knowledge are more desirable to tourists looking for authentic experiences (Acharya & Halpenny, 2013; McIntosh, 2004; Nagy et al., 2017).
- Genuine Occurrences: Travellers increasingly seek to understand a country via the eyes of its residents (Battour, 2018; Jeaheng et al., 2019; Mursid & Anoraga, 2022). This includes participating in traditional rituals, finding area handicrafts, and eating meals cooked using local recipes (Astuti et al., 2022; Iranmanesh et al., 2022).
- Community Involvement: Napatah and Azlan (2022) suggest that community-based tourism programmes, where locals showcase their cultural heritage, are a popular way to share local knowledge. In addition to improving the trip experience, this relationship develops respect between hosts and tourists (Jebbouri et al., 2022).
- Prioritising local knowledge enhances sustainable and culturally sensitive tourist practices (Ismail et al., 2014; Kristiyanto, 2017; Manara & Larasati, 2018; Muzakir & Suastra, 2024; Nyarota et al., 2022). Places that prioritise these qualities attract tourists, enhancing the destination's reputation (N. Sitorus, 2022; Su et al., 2020; Verinita, 2019).

Connection between Halal Destination Features and Destination Image according to Local Wisdom:

- **Authenticity and Cultural Integrity:** By honouring religious and cultural customs, halal destination features like serving halal cuisine and offering spaces for prayer are in line with local expertise (Pratiwi, 2023). The destination's reputation as a place that cherishes its cultural heritage and customs is improved by this authenticity (Amir Abdullah et al., 2020; Ghaderi et al., 2020; Khairunnisah et al., 2020; Seyfi et al., 2020).
- **Community Engagement:** Halal tourism typically partners with local communities to give authentic experiences for Muslim travellers (Han et al., 2018; Kurnia et al., 2023; Purwandani & Yusuf, 2021). This interaction helps to build the destination's image as a place where tourists can interact with people, learn about their customs, and participate in cultural activities.
- **Sustainability:** Halal tourism promotes local companies and addresses environmental concerns, aligning with local expertise (Battour, 2018; Moshin et al., 2020; Muttaqillah et al., 2018; Samad et al., 2022). This improves the destination's reputation as a responsible and ethical location to visit (crescentrating.com, 2023; Itang & Hadi Peristiwo, 2023).
- **Positive Impression and Image:** Integrating halal features based on local understanding enhances a destination's reputation among Muslim travellers (Han et al., 2018; Harianja et al., 2022; Kurnia et al., 2023; Manara & Larasati, 2018). Word-of-mouth recommendations and positive evaluations help to create a favourable destination image, which attracts more visitors over time (Cetin et al., 2014; Cong, 2021; Flavian et al., 2021).

- **Differentiation and Unique Selling Point:** Highlighting halal destination attributes based on local knowledge distinguishes a destination in the competitive tourism market. It distinguishes the destination as one-of-a-kind, providing authentic experiences tailored exclusively to the needs of Muslim visitors (Mulyadi et al., 2023).

4.4. The influence of Halal Destination Attributes on the Destination Image based on Local Wisdom

Features of halal destinations have a big influence on how people perceive a place. Research indicates that visitors' perceptions of the destination's value and contentment are significantly influenced by their Islamic beliefs and image (Zulaikhah et al., 2023). Additionally, it has been demonstrated that cultural, environmental, and socioeconomic representations significantly affect visitor pleasure and, as a result, destination loyalty (Haryeni et al., 2022). Additionally, the notion of halal tourism plays a crucial role in gauging the perception of a destination and impacting the intention to return (Chrismardani & Arief, 2022). Therefore, it is evident that halal destination features are crucial to establishing a destination's general reputation and attracting tourists.

Several researchers have also confirmed that. Sudigdo dan Khalifa (2020) demonstrates that, with the perception of tourism destinations acting as a mediating variable, the Islamic characteristics of Jakarta (worship facilities, halalness, and overall Islamic morals) positively impact travellers' decisions to visit. Raga (2020) demonstrates how the construction of the city of Bandung's image as a MICE destination is simultaneously impacted by the destination attribute. According to Puspita (2018), there is a positive correlation and influence of Halal tourism attributes on the destination image, interest in returning, and interest in recommending to others. According to Radito et al. (2016), positioning and product attributes have a big impact on brand image. Additionally, Radito et al. (2016) demonstrate that Product Attributes have a significant impact on Brand Image. According to Riyanto (2022), the Islamic characteristics of a place have a favourable and significant impact on the perception of halal tourism destinations.

4.5. The Influence of Halal Destination Attributes on Revisit Intention

The intention to return to halal travel is significantly influenced by the features of halal places. Research indicates that factors such as destination perception, destination trust, halal awareness, and halal-friendly features are significant determinants of travellers' intents to return (Sodawan & Hsu, 2022). Halal-specific features play a major role in determining tourists' intentions to return to halal places. This was verified by Pujiastuti et al. (2022), Han et al. (2018), Riyanto (2022), Ghani and Ratnasari (2022), and Battour et al. (2011).

According to Battour et al. (2011), Muslim travellers feel more at ease visiting a destination because of its Islamic characteristics. According to Riyanto (2022), the perception of halal tourism destinations is positively and significantly impacted by the Islamic characteristics of those places. Additionally, Riyanto (2022) demonstrates how the Islamic characteristics of a place influence visitor loyalty and repeat business.

In the meantime, Ghani and Ratnasari (2022) ascertain how the qualities of halal places impact their allure. As a result, Ghani and Ratnasari's research from 2022 showed how functional and emotional values, among other halal destination qualities, influenced tourists' judgements. The impact of location attractiveness on both practical and emotional value was also confirmed by the study. According to Ghani & Ratnasari (2022), halal destination qualities have an impact on Muslim tourists' propensity to return to halal places. According to Han et al. (2018), South Korea has halal-friendly features that are helpful in attracting repeat business. Pujiastuti et al. (2022), who discovered the influence of destination attributes on Return Visit Intention, supported Han's assertions.

5. Conclusion

Based on the literature review that was done it is understand that the link connecting Halal Destination Attributes and Destination Image based on Local Wisdom is synergistic. Destinations that incorporate halal-friendly amenities and services that respect customs and principles of culture can increase their authenticity, involve local communities, and develop a positive image among Muslim tourists. This integrated strategy not only draws more visitors, but it also encourages sustainable tourism practices and protects cultural assets, resulting in an advantageous outcome for both tourists and host communities. On the other side, Halal Destination Attributes are influencing the Muslim tourist in deciding Revisit Intention to a destination.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Author contribution statement

The first contributor contributes to the theme by describing and attaching data, while the other contributors help the first author analyse the difficulties raised.

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